

ISO 9000, SEI CAPABILITY MATURITY MODEL (CMM), AND CONTINUOUS SOFTWARE PROCESS IMPROVEMENT

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There are a number of ISO Standards which are applicable to software development, acquisition, maintenance, and quality. These are ISO 9001, ISO 9000-3, and the emerging ISO 12207 and SPICE standards. Many organizations implement these standards in order to be registered with ISO as being compliant with one or more of their various standards. There are good business reasons for doing so. In many parts of the world, registration as being compliant with one or a number of ISO standards is essential in order to conduct business in these countries. Duly-authorized representatives of ISO conduct audits of organizations to determine their compliance.

ISO 9001 is a quality system standard which is applicable to the design, manufacturing, installation, test, and maintenance of systems, typically under a two-party agreement. The text of the requirements of ISO 9001 are very much hardware system oriented.

ISO 9000-3 is a guidebook on applying the requirements of ISO 9001 to software development and maintenance organizations, and not a software quality system standard. It describes a number of elements that should be included in an organization's quality system for software. These are organized into three major areas: framework, life-cycle activities, and supporting activities. Examples of these elements include:

- Establishment of a Quality Program (framework)
- Corrective Action (framework)
- Contract Review (life-cycle activities)
- Development Planning (life-cycle activities)
- Design and Implementation (life-cycle activities)
- Maintenance (life-cycle activities)
- Configuration Management (supporting activities)
- Quality Records (supporting activities)
- Measurement (supporting activities)

For the most part, ISO 9000-3 and ISO 9001 specify only minimal requirements for the elements covered in these standards. Effectively, they require that the organization has a quality system and a quality plan that addresses these elements, and that the organization

specifies what practices it will apply in implementing these elements. Furthermore, there is a requirement that an organization be audited as part of the registration process. Periodic follow-up audits are conducted every six months subsequent to the initial registration to maintain the registration. Registered organizations must, therefore, demonstrate continuous compliance with their quality system documentation. Through the corrective action element of the standards, process improvement is addressed, although somewhat indirectly.

In essence, establishing compliance to the ISO standards plays a role in strategic quality planning. Registration is a lengthy process, involving the establishment of quality plans, procedures, etc.

Pre **ISO 9000, CMM, and CSP Improvement 57** liminary audits may be used as a means of determining the readiness for registration. The process of registration can take from one to two years from the date of inception to accomplish.

Another ISO standard, called SPICE (Software Process Improvement Capability dEtermination), is nearing completion. It is similar, in some respects, to the CMM in that it has an organization of maturity levels with defined key processes. It also has an assessment methodology associated with it, which will be in the public domain.

In its current form, the key process areas are selectable. Each software development organization is free to define which key processes they wish to be evaluated against.

SPICE is currently undergoing Phase 2 field trials. Formal release of SPICE is expected sometime in 1998. The CMM, by contrast, when compared to most of the ISO standards, is fairly prescriptive. As we will see in the next section, for each Key Process Area (KPA), the Key Practices define *what* practices the organization must be performing in order to have that KPA under control. The Key Practices don't define *how* things should be done only *what*. This leaves the organization free to choose whatever methodologies makes sense for the particular types of applications they produce. For example, for the Level 2 Software Project Planning KPA, one of the Key Practices requires the development organization to establish a software life cycle with predefined stages of manageable size for each project. There is nothing that mandates a waterfall model or a spiral model or incremental development, etc. In fact, at Level 2, each project is free

to utilize a different development cycle model, just as long as one is specified.

When compared to the requirements of ISO 9000-3, the CMM is definitely more prescriptive. The same is true if we compare it to the degree of rigor specified in ISO 12207. ISO 12207 is a software life cycle standard. It tends to be somewhere between ISO 9001 (or ISO 9000-3) and the CMM in its extent of specificity. ISO 12207 tends to cover many of the same kinds of items included in the CMM.

Like the comparison to 9000-3, the CMM has many areas of overlap with 12207, but there are also many areas that are unique to both standards. For instance, because 12207 is a life cycle standard, it covers maintenance more effectively than does the CMM. But the CMM does a more thorough job in covering specific software development practices (the "whats") that organizations should implement.

In 1987, the SEI published the first in a series of publications defining a Capability Maturity Model (CMM) for categorizing the capability of software organizations to develop software.

The work of the SEI in defining a Capability Maturity Model and accompanying assessment methodology is an important contribution. It has promoted significant improvements in quality and productivity, and has led to large cost savings.

In order to support these efforts, a metrics program was launched. The objectives of the program were to supply the process improvement teams working in these three areas designated by management with quantitative information. These metrics are the collected and tracked on a Software Development Management Dashboard (SDMD).

These findings by the assessment team later resulted in a recommended process improvement project to set up the MIO-Software Development Management Dashboard. The MIO dashboard was designed as a graphical display of metrics measuring dimensions identified as critical to MIO by management. It is used in management and technical meetings to identify areas for improvement and track progress towards targets and goals.

These findings and action items make MIO very typical of software development organizations. The next section provides statistics derived from the SEI's database from conducted assessments that support this claim.

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